

Short communication

FIRST RECORD OF *DIMORPHOCORIS BEIERI* WAGNER 1965 (HETEROPTERA: MIRIDAE) IN SERBIA

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Nine species of the genus *Dimorphocoris* have been recorded on the Balkan Peninsula: *D. beieri* Wagner, 1965 – Montenegro; *D. debilis debilis* (Reuter, 1880) – Greece; *D. fuscus* Joakimov, 1909 – Bulgaria; *D. gracilis* (Rambur, 1839) – Croatia; *D. lateralis* Reuter, 1901 – Greece; *D. sari* Linnavuori, 1992 – Greece; *D. saulii* Wagner, 1965 – Serbia, Slovenia; *D. schmidtii* (Fieber, 1858) – Slovenia and *D. tristis* (Fieber, 1861) – Greece (Wagner, 1965; Tamanini, 1972; Gogala, 1994; Vinokurov & Kanyukova, 1995; Ehanno, 1997).

Dimorphocoris saulii Wagner was previously recorded in Serbia on Mt. Stolovi (Protić, 2016). It was the only representative of the genus *Dimorphocoris* in the fauna of Serbia. An additional species from this genus, *Dimorphocoris beieri* Wagner, was collected in Serbia in the summer of 2019.

D. beieri is an endemic species from the Balkan Peninsula, so far described and recorded from Mt. Durmitor in Montenegro (Wagner 1965, 1973, Tamanini 1972, Protić *et al.* 1990, Ehanno 1997, Protić 2016). In July and September 2019, *Dimorphocoris beieri* was found in Serbia for the first time.

Sites where *D. beieri* Wagner was recorded in Serbia:

Mt. Vardenik: Veliki Strešer 31.07.2019. 2 ♂♂ leg. Aleksandar Stojanović

Mt. Vardenik: Veliki Strešer 03.09.2019. 2 ♂♂ leg. Bojana Nadaždin

All specimens were collected by sweep-netting. The material is deposited in the collections of the National History Museum, Belgrade.

D. beieri belongs to the “*gracilis*” group with macropterous males and brachypterous females (Linnavuori, 1992, Tataric & Cassis 2012).

More of the species of the genus *Dimorphocoris* have montane distribution, inhabiting high-mountain meadows at altitudes above 1000 m (Wagner, 1965; Gogala, 1994; Linnavuori, 1992). Specimens of *D. beieri* collected at Veliki Strešer, the highest peak of Mt. Vardenik (Figs. 1, 2), were also found in similar habitats. Disjunctive ranges are common in this genus.

Mt. Vardenik is situated in southeastern Serbia and belongs to the Rhodope mountain chain, which is the oldest mountain chain on the Balkan Peninsula. The mountains are composed of crystalline schist, with marble, granite and younger igneous rocks, which were already folded during the Paleozoic. Most of the Rhodopes are in southern Bulgaria, while parts of the chain are found in North Macedonia and Serbia. They lead from Marica R. in the east to the Dinaric and Shara-Pindus mountain chain in the west, as well as to the Carpathian-Balkan mountains in the northeast.

Veliki Strešer (1876 m) is the highest peak of Mt. Vardenik, inhabited by vegetation of low shrubs from the class *Vaccinio-Piceetea* and alpine-subalpine grassland formations dominated by *Carex* spp., *Festuca* spp., *Nardus* spp., *Sesleria* spp. and *Poa* spp. (Randelović & Zlatković, 2010).

The localities where *D. beieri* was collected are in the process of being included in a new protected area: PIO [Predeo Izuzetnih Odlika=Landscape of Exceptional Features] "Vardenik – Strešer". The importance of this locality was already recognized as it also hosts some strictly protected butterfly species: *Colias caucasica* Staudinger, 1871, *Polyommatus eros* (Ochsenheimer, 1808) and *Kirinia climene* (Esper, 1783), as well as the lizard *Zootoca vivipara* (Lichtenstein, 1823). All these faunistic records highlight the exceptional nature of this high-mountain habitat at Veliki Strešer (Tot *et al.*, 2017, Crnobrnja-Isailović *et al.*, 2013). The record of heteropteran *D. beieri* is an additional indicator of the presence of well-preserved important habitats in this area.

Figure 1. Mt. Vardenik: Veliki Strešer (1876 m) the highest peak. Photo by Miroslav Jovanović.

Figure 2. Veliki Strešer habitat of *Dimorphocoris beieri* Wagner. Photo by Miroslav Jovanović.

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References: Crnobrnja-Isailović, J., Dinov, J., Isailović, O., & Randelović, V. (2015). *Herpetozoa* 27 (3/4), 162-165; Ehanno, B. (1997). *Bulletin de la Société Scientifique de Bretagne* 66 (1995-1996), 3-88; Gogala, A. (1994). *Acta entomologica slovenica*, 2: 13-17; Linnavuori, R. E. (1992). *Entomologica Fennica* 3, 215-222; Protić, Lj., Gogala, A., & Gogala, M. (1990). *The Fauna of Durmitor*. Crnogorska akademija nauka i umjetnosti, Titograd, CANU Posebna izdanja 23, Odjeljenje prirodnih nauka 14, 279-313; Protić, Lj. (2016). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum*, 9, 95-105. doi:10.5937/hnhmb1609095P; Randelović, V., & Zlatković, B. (2010). *Odsek za biologiju i ekologiju, Prirodno-matematički fakultet, Univerzitet u Nišu*. 448 pp.; Tamanini, L. (1972). *Atti Della Società Italiana di Scienze Naturali e del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale di Milano* 113 (2), 117-132; Tarnic, N. J., & Cassis, G. (2012). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 164(3), 558-658; Tot, I., Đurić, M., & Popović, M. (2017). *Butterflies of Vlasina*. JP „Direkcija za građevinsko zemljište i puteve opštine Surdulica“, Surdulica; Vinokurov, N. N., & Kanyukova, E. V. (1995). Yakutian Scientific Centre, Yakutsk, 62 pp.; Wagner, E., (1965). *Reichenbachia*, 6: 33-66; Wagner, E., (1973). *Entomologische Abhandlungen Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde in Dresden*, 39, Supplement, 421 pp.

ПРВИ НАЛАЗ *DIMORPHOCORIS BEIERI* WAGNER 1965
(HETEROPTERA: MIRIDAE) У СРБИЈИ

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Извод

На Великом Стрешеру, највишем врху планине Варденик уловљена је нова врста за фауну Србије - *Dimorphocoris beieri* Wagner, 1965. Врста је ендемит Балканског полуострва, а осим Србије забележена је још и у Црној Гори на планини Дурмитор (Wagner 1965, 1973, Protić *et al.* 1990). Поред ове у Србији је забележена још једна врста истог рода - *D. saulii* Wagner, на планини Столови (Protić, 2016).

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